

Digital Twins in the Upstream Oil and Gas Industry: Trends, Applications, and Challenges

Mohammed Abderrahmane DADA ⁽¹⁾

(1): In Salah Gas Project - SH-Eni-Equinor joint venture.

SUMMARY

Digital twins are revolutionizing the oil and gas industry by enhancing efficiency, safety, and sustainability. Key trends include the integration of IoT, AI, and cloud computing, enabling predictive maintenance and real-time monitoring. Major players like Shell, BP, and Chevron are pioneering digital twin applications to optimize operations and reduce environmental impact. However, challenges such as legacy systems, data quality issues, scalability, and the need for skilled talent hinder widespread adoption. In Algeria, embracing digital twins could transform the energy sector, but success hinges on overcoming these challenges through strategic planning, infrastructure investment, and cultural change. The goal of this contribution is shed some light on the trends and challenges facing the deployment of “Digital Twins” technology in the oil and gas upstream sector.

Keywords: Digitalization, Digital Twins, O&G, Upstream, Trends, Applications, Challenges, GHG Emissions.

1. INTRODUCTION

Digitalization is revolutionizing industries worldwide, and the upstream oil and gas sector is no exception. A key player in this transformation is the use of digital twins—virtual counterparts of physical assets, systems, or processes. These digital replicas enable real-time monitoring, simulation, and optimization, leading to significant advantages such as increased operational efficiency, minimized downtime, and more informed decision-making.

The adoption of digital twin technology offers substantial benefits to the oil and gas industry. By providing simulation-driven insights, it can promote more sustainable practices, reduce emissions, and ensure better regulatory compliance. Additionally, digital twins enhance the efficiency of drilling operations by allowing virtual scenario testing. With the industry's extensive sensor networks, these virtual models facilitate comprehensive real-time monitoring and predictive maintenance, which in turn improves asset performance. This technology is particularly valuable in reducing costs, especially in decommissioning projects, and can help prevent expensive downtimes or environmental incidents. However, the full potential of digital twins can only be realized if the industry addresses challenges related to data quality, scalability, and the need for cultural change. As more companies invest in and integrate digital twin technologies, these virtual models are poised to become increasingly central to the future of the upstream sector. This is supported by a recent report from the consulting firm GlobalData, which projects that the global market for digital twin solutions will reach approximately \$154 billion by 2030 [1].

For countries like Algeria, which has a major stake in the oil and gas sector, embracing digital twins could lead to significant advancements in productivity, sustainability, and cost-effectiveness.

2. CURRENT TRENDS IN DIGITAL TWIN APPLICATIONS

Digital twins are increasingly being integrated at various stages of the exploration and production (E&P) lifecycle, with one of the most notable applications being predictive maintenance. By

continuously monitoring the performance of equipment and systems, digital twins can forecast potential component failures, enabling proactive maintenance that reduces downtime and extends the lifespan of assets.

The oil and gas industry, a colossal \$5 trillion global sector, is on the cusp of significant transformation through the adoption of digital twin technology. This technology offers substantial opportunities for optimization and efficiency across the industry's complex operations, with far-reaching implications for the global economy. Digital twins, which create virtual replicas of physical assets, can greatly enhance exploration projects—a key driver behind the \$136 billion in annual capital expenditures (CAPEX) in the U.S. oil and gas industry. By simulating drilling scenarios and analyzing real-time data, digital twins can inform decisions related to equipment, resource allocation, and strategies, leading to more cost-effective and safer exploration efforts. [2].

All these challenges can be tackled if investments in infrastructures and clear strategies are put in place, as well as having the workforce trained to get strong digital skills. According to a report published recently [3], digital twins have emerged as a game-changing technologies that can help solve these challenges. The market that has put in place by decision-makers, investors and industrials. This market, according to the same report, is driven by many incentives to cite the main:

- The global digital twin market in the oil and gas industry is expected to witness substantial growth in the coming years.
- The increasing adoption of IoT devices, advanced analytics, and cloud computing is driving the demand for digital twin solutions.
- The need for improved asset performance, reduced downtime, and enhanced safety and security is fueling the adoption of digital twins in the oil and gas sector.
- North America is expected to dominate the market due to the presence of major oil and gas companies and advancements in technology.
- The market is highly competitive, with several technology providers offering digital twin solutions tailored for the oil and gas industry.

Beyond streamlining capital-intensive projects, digital twins promise a shift in operational expenses as well. By constantly monitoring equipment health and predicting potential failures, they can facilitate predictive maintenance. This can significantly impact the bottom line, especially considering the variability in net margins across different segments of the industry in the digital twin in oil & gas market: integrated oil and gas companies tend to have the best net margins, followed closely by oil and gas production companies, while oil and gas services and equipment companies often have slimmer margins. Additionally, digital twins can play a role in optimizing production processes (where oil and gas production companies enjoy gross margins nearing 60%) and managing complex supply chains across this massive industry [2].

Through predictive simulations and process optimization, digital twins hold the potential for increasing operational efficiency, enhancing safety, and minimizing environmental impact – all critical factors that could shape the industry's future and its relationship with government and regulatory bodies [2].

3. APPLIED DIGITAL TWINS IN THE E&P INDUSTRY

The adoption of digital twins has delivered measurable benefits across the oil and gas industry, with leading companies investing in this technology to enhance their operations. Advancements in

IoT, AI, machine learning, and 3D modeling are driving the development of sophisticated digital twins, offering valuable insights for optimizing operations and improving asset management. As these technologies evolve, industry leaders are increasingly embracing digital twins to boost efficiency, safety, and sustainability, thereby positioning themselves for a more resilient and innovative future [3].

1). SHELL: Shell has been at the forefront of digital twin adoption, leveraging this technology to optimize operations across its offshore platforms and refineries. By integrating advanced analytics and machine learning, Shell has enhanced predictive maintenance and operational efficiency. One notable success is Shell's GeoSigns software, a digital twin application for seismic imaging, which played a pivotal role in discovering 10 million barrels of oil in the Gulf of Mexico, underscoring the potential of digital twins in exploration.

2). BP: BP has deployed digital twins across a range of assets, including pipelines and production facilities, to improve performance and mitigate operational risks. BP's APEX system, which creates digital twins of production systems, has revolutionized real-time monitoring and optimization. A notable achievement was in Trinidad and Tobago, where BP used APEX to reroute flows during pipeline maintenance, preserving significant production volumes that would have otherwise been lost.

3). CHEVRON: Chevron uses digital twins to enhance drilling operations and asset management. By creating detailed models of drilling equipment and subsurface environments, Chevron optimizes drilling performance and reduces downtime. The company has also partnered with Emerson and Microsoft to implement digital twins for optimizing heat exchanger maintenance schedules, resulting in substantial cost savings and improved operational reliability.

4). EQUINOR: Equinor has embraced digital twins to optimize its offshore operations. Using IoT sensors, advanced analytics, and AI, Equinor's digital twins reduce maintenance costs, enhance safety, and increase operational efficiency. A significant example is the digital twin of its Johan Sverdrup platform, which has been crucial in optimizing drilling processes under challenging conditions, such as managed-pressure drilling.

5). PETROBRAS: Petrobras has integrated digital twins into its offshore and onshore operations, focusing on enhancing asset management and operational efficiency. The technology enables real-time monitoring and predictive maintenance, which reduces downtime and improves safety. Petrobras is also exploring the use of digital twins to optimize production processes and minimize environmental impact.

6). ADNOC: The Ghasha mega-project, led by ADNOC, is pioneering the use of digital technologies and AI to optimize operations from subsurface to drill centers and ground facilities. This project is groundbreaking as it will be the world's first 100% unmanned offshore operation, utilizing high-tech sensors, drones, rail cameras, inspection robots, and digital twin technology to enhance operational efficiency and predictive maintenance for critical equipment¹.

7). ARAMCO: Within Aramco, numerous Process Digital Twins (PDTs) have been developed to optimize and integrate the company's hydrocarbon value chain. These PDTs can be physics-based, data-driven, or a hybrid of both, and they simulate actual processes with a deep understanding of historical performance and potential outcomes. PDTs provide insights into complex assets, enabling users to detect issues that may not be immediately apparent. These solutions are expected

¹ Courtesy: <https://adnoc.ae/en/our-projects/hail-ghasha/leveraging-technology>

to generate millions of dollars in annual benefits and play a crucial role in achieving the company's safety and sustainability goals [4].

4. CHALLENGES FOR IMPLEMENTING DIGITAL TWINS

A clear understanding of the challenges behind the implementation and deployment of digital twins is critical for O&G companies to fully get the benefits from them and avoid, in terms of investments, large capital expenditures [5, 6].

4.1. Technical Considerations

Despite the promising advantages of digital twins, their implementation in the upstream oil and gas industry comes with notable challenges. A primary hurdle is the need for high-quality, real-time data, as the accuracy and reliability of a digital twin are directly tied to the integrity of the data it processes. Integrating data from diverse sources and ensuring seamless interoperability can be both complex and costly. Issues such as inconsistent data quality, sensor malfunctions, and entrenched data silos can compromise the precision of digital twin predictions and the value of the insights generated.

The industry's traditional siloed approach presents another significant barrier. Transitioning to a more collaborative and data-driven environment requires a profound cultural shift within organizations, which can be difficult to achieve. Additionally, scalability remains a concern. Although digital twins have demonstrated success on individual projects, scaling their application across entire assets or operations demands extensive resources and careful coordination.

Furthermore, the adoption of digital twins is also hampered by concerns surrounding data security and privacy, especially in cloud-based systems. To encourage broader adoption, these issues must be effectively addressed. Digital twin systems need to be designed to manage vast data volumes, accommodate multiple users, and be flexible enough to adapt to evolving infrastructure needs. Meeting these requirements is crucial for the sustainable and successful deployment of digital twins in the industry.

4.2. Economic and Financial Considerations

Economic and financial considerations are pivotal in the adoption and implementation of digital twin technology within the oil and gas industry. One of the foremost concerns is the substantial initial investment required, which includes the costs associated with hardware, software, and the necessary infrastructure. Organizations need to perform a thorough cost-benefit analysis to determine the potential return on investment (ROI) from digital twin projects. This analysis is crucial in justifying the upfront expenditures and ensuring that the long-term financial benefits outweigh the initial costs.

For smaller companies or startups, securing the necessary funding for digital twin initiatives can be particularly challenging. Traditional financing options may be limited, making it essential to explore innovative funding strategies. Public-private partnerships, joint ventures, or grant programs could serve as viable solutions to overcome financial obstacles and encourage investment in this technology.

Moreover, conducting comprehensive economic impact assessments is critical to understanding the broader benefits of digital twin technology. These assessments should evaluate the potential for increased productivity, efficiency improvements, job creation, and overall industry competitiveness. By quantifying these economic impacts, companies and stakeholders can make

more informed decisions regarding the adoption of digital twin technology, ensuring that the financial investment contributes to the industry's long-term growth and success.

4.3. Regulatory and Ethical Challenges

Navigating the evolving regulatory landscape and addressing ethical concerns are crucial for the successful implementation of digital twin technology in the oil and gas industry. Compliance with regulatory requirements related to data privacy, security, and environmental standards is not just a legal obligation but a critical factor in mitigating risks associated with digital twin projects. As regulations continue to evolve, organizations must remain vigilant, continuously monitoring changes to ensure that their digital twin implementations meet the latest legal and regulatory standards. Failure to do so could result in significant legal and financial repercussions.

In addition to regulatory compliance, ethical considerations play a pivotal role in the deployment of digital twin technology. Issues such as data privacy, transparency, and fairness must be carefully managed to maintain trust among stakeholders. Organizations need to establish clear policies and guidelines that govern data usage, consent, and accountability. By proactively addressing these ethical concerns, companies can foster a culture of responsibility and transparency, thereby enhancing stakeholder confidence and ensuring the sustainable integration of digital twin technology into their operations.

4.4. Implementation

4.4.1. Strategic Planning

Integrating digital twin technology into existing oil and gas infrastructure requires a structured and comprehensive approach. Here's a breakdown of key considerations for effective integration:

- 1). **Assessment of Existing Infrastructure:** Start with a detailed evaluation of current assets, data systems, and operational processes. This involves mapping out where digital twin technology can provide the most benefit. Prioritize areas based on potential value and the feasibility of integration.
- 2). **Stakeholder Engagement:** Engage a broad range of stakeholders, including executives, engineers, operators, and IT professionals, from the outset. Collaboration is crucial for defining clear project goals, requirements, and success criteria. It's important to communicate the advantages of digital twins and secure alignment with the project's objectives.
- 3). **Resource Allocation:** Ensure adequate resources for the project, covering funding, personnel, and technological infrastructure. Create a realistic budget and timeline, accounting for costs related to software development, data acquisition, and staff training.
- 4). **Risk Identification and Mitigation:** Anticipate potential risks and challenges, both technical (e.g., data integration) and organizational (e.g., resistance to change). Develop contingency plans to address these risks and ensure a smooth implementation.

Each step requires careful planning and execution to ensure that the integration of digital twin technology enhances operational efficiency and achieves the desired outcomes.

4.4.2. Technological Integration

Integrating digital twins with existing IT and operational technology (OT) systems is essential for maximizing their effectiveness and ensuring seamless operation.

- 1) **Develop robust data integration strategies** to connect digital twins with data sources across the organization. This may involve implementing data lakes, APIs, or middleware

solutions to aggregate and harmonize data from disparate sources. Ensure data quality and consistency to maintain the accuracy and reliability of digital twin models.

2) Ensure that digital twin systems are interoperable with existing IT and OT systems to facilitate data exchange and collaboration. Adopt industry standards and protocols to seamlessly integrate other systems and platforms. This may involve working closely with vendors and technology partners to ensure compatibility and interoperability.

3) Design digital twin solutions that are scalable and flexible to accommodate future growth and changes in infrastructure. Implement modular architectures and scalable cloud-based platforms that adapt to evolving requirements and accommodate new data sources and technologies.

4) Implement robust security measures to protect digital twin systems from cyber threats and unauthorized access. This includes implementing encryption, access controls, and authentication mechanisms to safeguard sensitive data. Ensure compliance with data privacy regulations such as GDPR to protect the privacy rights of individuals.

4.4.3. Skills and Training

Integrating digital twins with existing IT and operational technology (OT) systems is crucial for their optimal performance and seamless operation. Here's a strategic approach to achieve effective integration:

1). **Data Integration Strategies:** Develop comprehensive strategies to connect digital twins with various data sources across the organization. Consider using data lakes, APIs, or middleware solutions to aggregate and harmonize data from diverse sources. Ensure data quality and consistency to uphold the accuracy and reliability of digital twin models.

2). **System Interoperability:** Ensure that digital twin systems can work seamlessly with existing IT and OT systems by adopting industry standards and protocols. Collaborate with vendors and technology partners to guarantee compatibility and smooth data exchange.

3). **Scalability and Flexibility:** Design digital twin solutions with scalability and flexibility in mind. Utilize modular architectures and cloud-based platforms that can adapt to future growth, evolving requirements, and new data sources and technologies.

4). **Security Measures:** Implement stringent security protocols to protect digital twin systems from cyber threats and unauthorized access. This includes encryption, access controls, and authentication mechanisms to secure sensitive data. Ensure compliance with data privacy regulations, such as GDPR, to safeguard individuals' privacy rights.

By addressing these aspects, organizations can enhance the effectiveness of their digital twin technology and ensure its integration with existing systems is both seamless and secure.

4.4.4. Change Management

Effectively managing the organizational change needed for the successful implementation of digital twin technology is essential for overcoming resistance and ensuring adoption. Here's a structured approach to managing this change:

1). **Change Readiness Assessment:** Evaluate the organization's preparedness for adopting digital twin technology. Identify potential obstacles and assess stakeholders' concerns and motivations. Develop targeted strategies to address resistance and foster support for digital twin initiatives.

2). **Communication and Stakeholder Engagement:** Clearly communicate the advantages of digital twin technology and actively engage stakeholders throughout the transition. Provide transparent updates on project goals, objectives, and anticipated outcomes. Encourage feedback and address concerns to ensure stakeholder perspectives are considered and valued.

3). **Training and Support:** Offer comprehensive training and support to help employees adjust to digital twin technology. Conduct workshops, seminars, and hands-on training sessions to familiarize staff with new tools, processes, and workflows. Provide continuous support and resources to assist employees in overcoming challenges and achieving success.

4). **Leadership and Sponsorship:** Secure active sponsorship and support from organizational leaders for digital twin initiatives. Ensure senior leaders are committed to the success of these projects and empower project teams with the authority and resources needed to drive change and address obstacles.

In summary, the successful implementation of digital twin technology in the oil and gas industry hinges on strategic planning, effective technological integration, skill development, and robust change management. By adopting these strategies, organizations can unlock the full potential of digital twin technology, driving innovation, efficiency, and competitive advantage within the industry.

5. ACHIEVING SUSTAINABILITY AND MITIGATING GHG EMISSIONS

Going green is no longer optional for oil and gas companies; it has become imperative. The oil and gas sector accounts for 42% of global emissions, both directly and indirectly [xx]. In response, governments are rapidly implementing measures to curb carbon emissions. Currently, 40 countries have adopted carbon pricing policies, such as carbon taxes or emission trading schemes (ETS), to drive down emissions. In the EU, the carbon price surged to a record €66 per ton in November 2021 [7], with proposals to extend the price to previously exempt sectors like aviation and maritime. China has launched its national ETS as part of its commitment to achieve net-zero emissions by 2060, and Singapore has introduced a carbon tax at S\$5 per ton, becoming the first South-East Asian country to do so [8].

With these stringent regulations, oil and gas companies are taking proactive measures to mitigate risks by adopting climate-friendly strategies. For instance, the world's fourth-largest oil company by revenue has committed to achieving net-zero emissions by 2050 and is diversifying into renewable energy. Other top oil firms are similarly shifting their focus away from upstream production investments. However, despite these bold declarations, skepticism remains about the genuine progress of these companies toward decarbonization.

Digital solutions offer significant benefits in the fight against climate change. A report made by PwC for Microsoft highlights that AI applications in developing "Digital Twin" systems can potentially reduce global greenhouse gas emissions by up to 4%, with the energy sector poised to benefit the most [9]. Here are several ways in which digital technologies can assist the oil and gas sector in achieving its sustainability goals:

5.1. Methane Leak Detection and Prevention

Methane leaks are imperceptible to the naked eye, necessitating specialized equipment such as surveillance cameras, sensors, drones, and, in some cases, more costly methods like aircraft and satellites for detection. AI can enhance leak detection by analyzing the characteristics of oil wells and developing algorithms to identify variables associated with a higher risk of leakage. For

instance, a study by the University of Vermont, which examined 38,391 wells, utilized machine learning to pinpoint three critical vulnerabilities: (1) wells that deviate from a vertical alignment, (2) wells employing outdated drilling practices, and (3) wells with larger diameters. This study demonstrated a high accuracy rate of up to 87% [10]. Leveraging AI in this manner enables companies to more effectively inspect and monitor high-risk wells and informs the design of future wells to minimize leakage risks.

5.2. Oil Well Maximization

Maximizing well production can lead to fewer wells needing to be drilled, thereby reducing carbon emissions. The availability of data from the National Data Repository (NDR) allows oil and gas companies to cut down on effort, cost, and risks associated with exploration and production. However, these NDRs hold vast amounts of data in various formats. For example, the U.K.'s NDR spans 130 terabytes, equivalent to 8 years' worth of HD movies [11]. Analyzing such an enormous volume of data is beyond human capability, which is where AI becomes crucial.

5.3. Emission Prediction

AI can assist oil and gas companies in forecasting future carbon emissions by analyzing historical data alongside variables such as operational practices and market demand. This capability enables companies to anticipate emissions more accurately and make necessary adjustments to mitigate their environmental impact.

6. THE POTENTIAL OF DIGITAL TWINS FOR ALGERIA'S E&P INDUSTRY

For Algeria, a country with a significant oil and gas industry, the adoption of digital twins and broader digitalization efforts could be transformative. The Algerian energy sector is heavily reliant on its hydrocarbon resources, and improving the efficiency and sustainability of these operations is crucial for the country's economic future.

Digital twins could play a critical role in optimizing Algeria's exploration and production activities. By implementing predictive maintenance strategies, Algerian operators could significantly reduce downtime and maintenance costs, leading to higher production efficiency. Additionally, the use of digital twins in drilling operations could enhance safety and reduce operational risks, particularly in challenging environments.

Moreover, digital twins could help Algeria address some of the environmental challenges associated with oil and gas production. By simulating various operational scenarios, digital twins can help identify the most sustainable practices, reducing the environmental impact of E&P activities.

Algeria's E&P hydrocarbon industry, dominated by the state-owned enterprise, is still at an embryonic stage with regards to digital transformation. There is still a wide and long effort to perform in order to renew already existing yet obsolete data infrastructures or deploy completely novel technologies that incorporate advanced information technology systems along with robust data management and analysis capabilities. The Sonatrach legacy Information and Communications Technology (ICT) infrastructure supports various workloads but responds only to service requirements across the upstream, middle, and downstream phases of the oil and gas industry and the functional departments of each subsidiary. The legacy ICT system lacks unified planning, which leads to different problems such as:

- **Interoperability:** The Sonatrach has five data centers that are discrete and operate independently of one another. Core services are deployed in a single data center and lack Disaster Recovery (DR) measures, which makes it difficult to ensure service continuity.
- **Compatibility:** Sonatrach has more than 200 subsidiaries and more than 10 horizontal functional departments, and IT hardware is provided by different vendors. Information has to be manually transferred through Excel spreadsheets or other electronic reports, limiting mobile access and resulting in data silos between departments and subsidiaries.

To address these challenges, Sonatrach has partnered with Huawei to advance its digital transformation through a three-phase strategy [12]:

- 1- **Huawei Cloud Stack (HCS):** This phase integrates existing IT resources, removing resource silos and enabling unified resource management. It allows for on-demand provisioning across multiple data centers and facilitates rapid service deployment.
- 2- **SAP Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) System:** Deployed on the cloud platform, this system centralizes management of key business modules such as finance, HR, asset management, budget management, and logistics. It fosters seamless collaboration and data sharing between upstream and downstream operations, significantly enhancing the efficiency of management and operational processes.
- 3- **Innovative Service Platforms and Big Data Services:** This step focuses on the development and testing of new services. By utilizing data-value mining, Huawei supports the evolution of digitally enhanced oil fields. Their full-lifecycle processing capabilities—encompassing collection, storage, computing, management, and utilization—transform data resources into valuable assets.

Upon completion of these steps, Sonatrach will be well-positioned to implement a range of advanced solutions, including the integration of digital twin technology.

7. CONCLUSION

Digital twins mark a significant leap in the digital transformation of the upstream oil and gas industry, bringing notable advancements in efficiency, safety, and sustainability. The sector's growing recognition of digital solutions' potential is evident as major oil companies invest in technology start-ups to stay competitive. However, technology maturity alone does not guarantee successful digitalization. Key challenges such as legacy systems, digital talent shortages, a lack of agile culture, and difficulties in setting clear business priorities are more critical to overcome. Thus, we are only at the beginning of this transformative journey.

For Algeria, adopting digital twin technology offers a chance to greatly enhance the productivity and environmental performance of its exploration and production sector. To fully leverage these technologies, Algeria must address challenges related to data quality, scalability, and cultural change. By investing in infrastructure and fostering a collaborative, data-driven culture, Algeria can emerge as a leader in digital transformation within the oil and gas industry.

The success of a digital twin hinges on its ability to integrate existing data and derive actionable insights. Current data acquisition platforms often lack standardized data protocols, leading to structured, semi-structured, or unstructured data that can be challenging to consolidate into a unified database. Addressing this issue involves establishing standard data protocols and implementing a data warehouse for secure storage. Advanced data analytics tools are then necessary to analyze these data effectively.

A well-implemented digital twin should provide custom insights tailored to each user's needs, avoiding the distraction of redundant data. Implementing user profiles can help by defining specific insights required by each operator. Additionally, the development of a digital twin should start with an initial site survey and continue through all stages of a project—exploration, appraisal, development, production, and abandonment. Maintaining both hardware and software throughout the facility's lifecycle is crucial and can be managed by a multidisciplinary project team.

8. REFERENCES

- [1] Report Shows Digital Twins Gaining Rapid Acceptance in Oil and Gas Operations [Online], 2024. <https://jpt.spe.org/report-shows-digital-twins-gaining-rapid-acceptance-in-oil-and-gas-operations>.
- [2]: Digital Twin in Oil & Gas Market is Poised to Reach USD 912.1 Million by 2032 [Online], 2024. <https://www.globenewswire.com/news-release/2024/04/02/2855968/0/en/Digital-Twin-in-Oil-Gas-Market-is-Poised-to-Rreach-USD-912-1-Million-by-2032-Asset-Monitoring-and-Maintenance-Segment-Control-19-Revenue-Share-Says-Astute-Analytica.html>
- [3] Digital Twin in Oil and Gas Market Analysis – Industry Size, Share, Research Report, Insights, COVID-19 Impact, Statistics, Trends, Growth & Forecast 2024-2032 [Online], 2024. <https://markwideresearch.com/digital-twin-in-oil-and-gas-market/>
- [4]: A. H. Al Ghazal, G. A. Winter, A. M Al Nutaifi, A. A. Al Shaikh, T. A. Altook and Y. He: Saudi Aramco's Process Digital Twin: Advances & Implementation Strategy. ADIPEC, Abu Dhabi, UAE, October 2022. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.2118/211026-MS>.
- [5]: A. W. Esiri, O. O. Sofoluwe and A. Ukato: Digital Twin Technology in Oil and Gas Infrastructure: Policy Requirements and Implementation Strategies. Journal of Engineering Science and Technology, Vol 5, N°6, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.51594/estj/v5i6.1221>.
- [6]: T. R. Wanasinghe, L. Wroblewski, B. K. Petersen, R. G. Gosine, L. A. James, O. De Silva, G. K. I. Mann, and P. J. Warrian: Digital Twin for the Oil and Gas Industry: Overview, Research Trends, Opportunities, and Challenges. IEEE Access, Vol 8, 2020.
- [7]: The Future Is Now: How Oil and Gas Companies Can Decarbonize. McKinsey & Company [Online], 2020. <https://www.mckinsey.com/industries/oil-and-gas/our-insights/the-future-is-now-how-oil-and-gas-companies-can-decarbonize>.
- [8]: EU Carbon Prices Hit Record High After COP26, The Financial Times [Online], 2021. <https://www.ft.com/content/f3d33f16-9e8c-4657-8ca5-c988464a55c7>.
- [9]: How AI Can Enable a Sustainable Future, Microsoft, 2024.
- [10]: J. R. Wakefield: UVM Study Is First to Predict Which Oil and Gas Wells Are Leaking Methane [Online]. UVM Today, 2018. <https://www.uvm.edu/news/story/uvm-study-first-predict-which-oil-and-gas-wells-are-leaking-methane>.
- [11]: U. Ali: OGA Launches UK's First Oil and Gas National Data Repository [Online]. Offshore Technology, 2019. <https://www.offshore-technology.com/news/oga-national-data-repository/>.
- [12]: Sonatrach Transforms Its Oilfields in Algeria [Online], Huawei, ICT Insights, Issue 25. https://e.huawei.com/fr/ict-insights/global/ict_insights/201902271023/Success-Story/201904170833